

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

Muhammad Mullazai

MS Scholar, Faculty of Languages and Literature, Lasbela University of Agriculture,
Water and Marine Sciences, Uthal, Balochistan, Pakistan

Email: mohammadmullazai84@gmail.com

Zahid Ali

Associate Professor, Department of English Language and Literature, Government
College University Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan

Email: zahid.ali@gcu.edu.pk

Muhammad Shoaib Khan

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Government College University
Hyderabad, Sindh, Pakistan

Email: dr.m.shoaib@gcu.edu.pk

Faraz Ahmed

MS Scholar, Faculty of Languages and Literature, Lasbela University of Agriculture,
Water and Marine Sciences, Uthal, Balochistan, Pakistan

Email: farazsarwar53@gmail.com

Received on: 18-07-2023

Accepted on: 20-08-2023

Abstract

The core purpose of this current study is to explore and analyze the Argument/Thematic structure of Balochi verbs. This present study pursues to see that how various arguments or noun phrases in are assigned agent as well as theme theta roles by Balochi verbs. The study explores if agent as well as theme theta roles exist in various sentences of the Balochi language. Using Carnie's (2007) theory of Theta Roles, it intends to answer the research question: How Balochi verbs assign agent and theme theta roles to their arguments? The data are collected from natural verbal/oral form of Balochi sentences. It is important to note that the agreement among a verb and its arguments is an important aspect to learn any language. In order to analyze agent and theme theta roles in Balochi; each verb phrase is thereby analyzed in detail with respect to argument/thematic structure to find agent as well as theme theta roles in the Balochi sentences. The qualitative method has been applied along with descriptive and analytical research designs. Balochi agents are more flexible in terms of place and position in the verbal form. As compared to English, Balochi agents can be used at the beginning, middle, or the end position in

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

spoken form of Balochi sentences. The extensive study therefore finds that Balochi language has both agent and theme theta roles which is like that of English.

Keywords: Argument/Thematic structure, Balochi, English, Agents, Themes.

Introduction

The day we learn human language, we are looking what some may describe the 'human essence' the discerning capabilities of brain that are, as far as we comprehend, incomparable to man (Chomsky: language and mind, 1996). Language is used as a source of communication and interaction with each other equally in written and spoken form. Language is a method of symbols; its purpose is to communicate with each other. Each language has a different structure. The structure of Balochi language is different from other languages of the world. Balochi has an SOV structure (subject, object, verb) which is different from English and many other languages.

The theory of Carnie addresses the particular semantic associations among a verb and its arguments. Verbs allocate the thematic roles or theta roles to every argument or noun phrases that is necessary (should be contained within the verb phrase).

In the words of Badal Khan and Jahani (2013), Balochi language is one of the most prominent and larger languages among Western Iranian languages. Elfenbein (1997) states that the derivation of Balochi language drawn in the Iranian languages of north-western set of Indo-European kinfolk. In the words of Jahani (2013), Balochi language possesses three main types of verbs, and they are transitive verbs, intransitive verbs and within transitive verb we have ditransitive verbs.

Enormously, there are lots of books, records, paper works, articles, on Phonology, Morphology, as well as parts of speech; however, there is little or no scholarly attention has been given to syntax. No scholarly attention has been given to the aspects of Balochi verbs in addition to how their arguments are assigned to agent as well as theme theta roles by Balochi verbs. The aspects declared directly above and have constantly overseen from the previous to the present time. The writers of Balochi grammar compose about differences in dialectal variation, parts of speech, methods of learning the morphological in addition to syntactical rules, syntax, semantics, and grammar (Zahid, A., 2016; Ahmed, M., & Veesar, 2022; Ali, Z., 2021; Ali, Z., & Azam, 2021; Ali, Z., Roonjho, Z., & Brohi, 2021).

As a result, the purpose of this study is to establish Balochi verbs' Argument/Thematic Structure with respect to agent as well as theme theta roles. In this concern, it will be an attempt to an additional work in Balochi grammar especially in the area of syntax as well as semantics.

Origin of Balochi Language

Genuine study mechanisms have been prepared on Balochi language and outcome displays that it is a share of the northwestern set of Iranian languages beside with Zazaki Kurdish, Gilaki Mazandarani, and Talyshi (Axenove, 2006, Jahani, 2003). The work of Mackenzie (1961) is also witnessed that the speakers of Iranian languages Persian, Balochi and Kurdish have been in neighboring connection geologically and ethnologically. This connection can be observed by the works of Windfuhr (1975). He created out that numerous associations among Persian Kurdish and Balochi on traditional.

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

The writer additionally illuminates that the Balochi language partakes its derivation from the ancient Parthian and Middle languages. Simultaneously, Balochi language is there throughout 200 B.C to 700 A.D. Grierson (1921). Balochi language is frequently the sameness of further Iranian languages representing a closer connection to the antique language of the Avesta than to the ancient Persian. The official language of the Achaemendies from that the recent Persian is leaned directly. It being an ethnic form of speech which has established its own shapes from the initial periods.

Additionally, Shad (2011) then categorized Balochi language into three foremost dialects which are Makrani dialect, Rakhshani dialect and Kohe Sulamani dialect.

Balochi language is enriched in expressions, sayings, words, proverbs and idiomatic phrases, cradlesongs, folk, melodies, and traditional literature. Balochi language has many authors, poets, scholars, investigators, and linguists as well. The most crucial literary form was verbal literature. In the words of Badal khan and Jahani (2013), there was not practice of writing Balochi till a century ago. In the pre-literate culture of Baloch, Persian was there for record observance entirely. Balochi is identified as a sequence of dialects in the literature part studies and linguistics, for the greatest part commonly comprehensible, changing in vocabulary and the grade of inspiration from nearby languages predominantly Persian (Elfenbein, 1989a & 1989b).

Research Concern/Purpose

The aim of this research work is to describe, analyze as well as explore the argument structure in term of agent as well as theme theta roles in the Balochi language. The assignment of agent plus theme theta roles in Balochi sentences may help us understand this phenomenon. Several young grammarians as well as linguists did their work usually on Syntax, Morphology and Semantics but argument structure and theta roles are still missing by contemporary authors of Balochi grammar. In this concern, it is an attempt to an additional work in Balochi grammar especially in the field of syntax. The corresponding study deals with the analytical study of argument structure with respect to Balochi verbs.

The current study focuses to explore the use of argument structure with respect to agent as well as theme theta roles of Balochi verbs. For the meantime, this analytical study will capture praiseworthy opportunities to bring to the world of linguists a very prominent and key feature for this vital language.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this research is to examine and establish the agent and theme theta roles of Balochi verbs. It tries to understand the structure of noun phrases in Balochi and to understand the thematic structure of the arguments that illustrates agent as well as theme theta roles and the thematic relations. It also tries to examine how Balochi verbs allot agent and theme theta roles as well as thematic relation to their arguments.

Verbs in Balochi

In the words of Jahani, there are three various types of verbs in Balochi, they are simple verbs, preverbal verbs, as well as complex (or phrasal) verbs. There is no syntactic difference between these types of verbs. There is only one verb in simple verbs. For instance, warag 'to

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

eat or to drink' rawag 'to go'. Preverbal verbs are those kinds of verbs that have a verb together with a preverb that definitely includes an additional element of location are added to the fundamental meaning of the verb. For instance, dar barag 'to learn'. Additionally, the verbs comprise of a verb that has fundamentally lost its original meaning a nominal element (a noun, adjective or adverb) as well as (a light verb) that conveys the core meaning are called complex verbs. For instance, jeta kanag 'to separate', habar kanag 'to speak' etc. There also be a significant syntactical variance among transitive as well as intransitive verbs. A transitive verb has the capabilities of carrying a direct object. The examples are warag 'to eat', kanag 'to do' but an intransitive verb does not have the capabilities of taking an object. The examples are ayag 'to come', rawag 'to go', bayag 'to be, to become' as well as kapag 'to fall'. Therefore, simple verbs are determined by the transitivity of complex verbs as well as preverbal verbs.

Theta Roles and Argument Structure

Argument structure establishes the connection amongst predicates (VPs) and its arguments (NPs) (Reinhart, 2003). The verbs are the most vital and substantial element of the sentence as it gives the thematic role to the arguments at syntactic as well as semantic levels (Dowty, 1991). Therefore, the predicates or verb phrases allot various theta roles and thematic relations to the arguments. Commonly, argument structure is mainly the grouping of syntactic in addition to semantic structures; in which syntactic structure illustrates arguments or entities and semantic structure shows situations. The syntactic structure is identified by the structure of the sentence (Borer, 2005; Ackerman, 2013).

The subject or an external argument like an 'agent' in common is broadly considered to be or widely accepted to stand as the highest theta roles among others hierarchy of thematic structure (Jackendoff, 1972; Grimshaw, 1990). It must be noticeable that verbs assign theta roles to various arguments in any sentence are governed by argument structure. It is actually the verb that assign various theta role to each of the argument or noun phrase in a sentence. Definitely, thematic roles are presided by the help of thematic structure that in a sentence the arguments are allocated because of the verb. Therefore, a verb receives noun phrase in accordance to the condition or state uttered through the verb as of its sense (Haegeman, 1994; 2013; Hammer, Coene, Hamamatsu, 2013).

Theta Roles and Thematic Relations

Gruber (1965) was the first to explain the thematic relations in his doctoral thesis in which Jackendoff (1972) took it to peak and later many other linguists applied this theory to many other languages as well (Cowper, 1992). A thematic relation can appear at any points in the sentence because it is not restricted to only one place. A component might allot a single or more than a single thematic relation to the certain arguments. Moreover, the names "thematic relations" as well as "theta roles" are sometimes utilized or mixed up with each that is a major fault. Agent is taken by some verbs and others as sources, goals etc. However, it implies that the lexical access for each verb has to classify how many figures of noun phrases it receives and which "noun phrase" has which thematic relations. The doer of the action gets the agent theta role while the same subject or noun phrase might get more than a single thematic relation. In contrast, the explanation of theta roles is exactly defined in syntactic words. It is

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

actually theta role that assigns one role to each noun phrase in a sentence. It has a number of thematic relations that are allocated by a particular component to a specific point. In other words, it must be noted that any theta role might be comprised of a single or exceeding the thematic relation that might get more than one thematic relation, but essentially all of arguments that get more than one thematic relation are accurate in terms of argument structure (Cowper, 1992).

Simultaneously, Poole (2012) claims that DPs/NPs and sometimes PPs come in arguments whereas verbs, adjectives and prepositions come in predicates. He gives mathematical example of 'the equal sign' by comparing the predicate. In his words, a predicate takes two arguments, and they are equivalent with each other. Concerning argument structure, he also claims that according to the function and position in any sentence by considering the state of the verb each argument is allotted theta roles. Although, there are some intransitive verbs that can take only one argument, there are some transitive verbs that can take two or more arguments, whereas there are also such ditransitive verbs that can take three or more arguments. Thus, the methods are indicated by the idea of the semantic role by which the sentences are defined and the condition, task, state are supported by the reference of the noun phrase. The semantic role is not an innate property of a noun phrase however a specified noun phrase may have various semantic roles in various sentences.

1) *Ali kills the bird.*

(Transitive verb) [VP=NP+NP] (Haegeman, 1994)

In the above sentence, there are two arguments to talk about '*Ali*' and '*the bird*' are semantic participants of the verb '*kills*' and its core syntactic arguments- the subject and the direct object.

The agent is the Argument '*Ali*' the doer of the action. This argument is performing the action of killing a bird. The second argument '*the bird*' is the theme that goes through an action is being killed.

Research Methodology

In this research work both descriptive and exploratory methods were applied. This work has employed qualitative method of research (Creswell, 2013; Neuman, 2005; Kumar, 2011; 2014). In order to understand the terms, nature and the function of the verbs, the natural Balochi language spoken form or verbal form is nominated. The aim of this research is to study, describe and explore how arguments or noun phrases are assigned to agent and theme theta roles by different Balochi verbs. Descriptive research has been employed to describe the features of a population, phenomenon, or situation while the name exploratory research indicates which purely means to explore the research question.

The data are collected through interviews from individuals of native Balochi speakers. Unstructured interviews are the widely used techniques to collect primary data in any language. The participants are asked personal questions, their names and about their family first. They have also been asked about their professional lives, and the participants had enough confident to communicate more freely, frankly, fluently, confidently in a natural way. The data were gathered from verbal form of Balochi language sentences (spoken only). Such verbal form was selected in order to understand the nature of the verb and then the

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

application of argument structure with respect to agent as well as theme theta roles plus thematic relations which are assigned to each noun phrase by the predicate of Balochi sentences. Data collections were used alone or in combination to answer the research questions.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework projected by Andrew Carnie (2007) is applied for the present work. For establishing the Agent as well as Theme Theta Roles in consort with Thematic Relations for the arguments of the verbs, a theory namely 'Theta Role or Thematic Structure' proposed by Carnie was applicable and therefore it was applied. The theory of Carnie addresses the particular semantic associations among a verb and its arguments. Verbs allocate the thematic roles or theta roles to every argument or noun phrases that is necessary (should be contained within the verb phrase). Theta theory needs that theta criterion theory be satisfied and that it must be permitted for a verb to be used and worked grammatically. Thematic relations relate to the nature of the association among the meanings of the verb as well as the noun. The verbs want a number of arguments which then get theta roles (that is entirely syntactic concept). The syntactic associations are theta roles and the concerns to the semantic thematic relations (Carnie, 2007).

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed with the support of theoretical framework 'Theta Roles or Thematic Structure' projected by Andrew Carnie (2007). The Balochi verbs along with their forms were defined, analyzed, and described to understand their task, place, and significance in the sentences. The data were also analyzed in order to understand how Balochi verbs allot theta roles (similarly known as theta relations) to the arguments. Additionally, the data in this research were also analyzed to see how the settings of the verbs pay with respect to the sense of the verbs in a sentence.

Theta-Criterion/Grid theory

In the words of Chomsky (1981), the Theta-Criterion theory can be explained as; every argument permits only one Theta-role as well as every Theta-role is allotted to only a single argument.

Thematic Relations and Agent Theta Roles

The definition illustrates that the thematic roles, or theta roles (θ -role), have a connection among predicates with their arguments. An agent is the performer or the one who does an action. They can be subjects and may also come in other positions. Similarly, Agent is the one who can carry out an action. Consequently, arguments stand in various semantic associations with the verb. According to this principle, there must be one to one agreement among arguments with their Theta- roles. In order understand the connection among arguments with their theta role let's consider the following example 2.

2) *Joseph kills the animal.*

Here the NP [**Joseph**] is allotted the Theta role "**agent**", while the NP [the animal] is allotted

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

the θ -role ‘theme’. It must be noted that one argument has one theta role and more than one thematic relation. Hence, an argument that takes two Theta-roles or a θ -role, which is allotted to two arguments, would violate the rules of the Theta-Criterion; and thus, the sentence is not considered to be grammatically correct.

Now let’s take look at the following Balochi sentences that how verbs assign the agent theta roles as well as thematic relations to the arguments in the following sentences.

Table 1: Example (3) presents an intransitive verb in Balochi sentence, the arguments (NPs) of the predicates (VPs), and the assignment of agent theta roles as well as thematic relations to the arguments of the verbs.

Sentence	Sentence
Description	
Roman script	<i>Ida man Lasbela Universitya MS kanega un.</i>
Transliteration	<i>Ida=Here; mn=I;=Lasbela university; a=in Lasbela university;=MS; kaneg=do; =aun=am.</i>
Translation	<i>I am doing MS here in Lasbela University.</i>

The verb phrase ‘**kanegaon=am doing**’ is a transitive verb. An action carried out by a transitive verb is transferred from its own subject to its object. It requires two arguments. One comes at the place of subject and the other comes at the place of object. It specifies who (subject) is doing what (object). The fundamental form of the verb ‘**kanega=doing**’ is ‘**kanag=to do**’ and it’s a combination of two morphemes ‘**kanaga**’ which is the main verb of the sentence and a copula, inflection, or bound morpheme ‘**un**’ is attached with the stem of the main verb to express the aspect of the tense. However, through this inflection we come to know that the aspect is progressive. The suffix ‘**un**’ agreement also shows singular argument. The above sentence states two different arguments and both of them are singulars. The argument ‘**mn=I**’ is a first-person singular that is uttered as a common noun in place of subject. Consequently, it can be said that the performer of the action of doing something in this sentence is the subject or the agent ‘**mn=I**’. Therefore, the verb ascertains this argument as an agent theta role as well as an agent thematic relation.

The other argument ‘**MS**’ is merely the name of the degree (a proper noun) and lacks the living quality to carry out an action. This argument serves just as the sentence’s object. It has undergone an action and serves as the sentence’s main focus. Therefore, the verb allots this argument as the theme theta role as well as the theme thematic relation.

Table 2: Example (4) presents an intransitive verb in Balochi sentence, the arguments (NPs) of the predicates (VPs), and the assignment of agent theta roles as well as thematic relations to the arguments of the verbs.

Sentence	Sentence
Description	
Roman script	<i>Marchi hama yaja botegaa.</i>
Transliteration	<i>Marchi=today; hama=we; yaja=gather; bote=have; ga=agreement.</i>
Translation	<i>Today, we have gathered.</i>

The verb ‘**yaja=gather**’ in Balochi language is a transitive verb, but here it is used as an intransitive verb that does not need an object to forward action (from the subject to the

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

object). The root form of verb **'yaja'** is also **'yaja'** a bound morpheme that cannot be used alone as a verb to complete a sentence on its own, so for the verb in a sentence to have its full meaning, a free morpheme **'botega'** is necessary, therefore **'yaja'** along with **'botega'** is used here to give appropriate meaning to the verb in a sentence. There is double constructed verb in the sentence, or auxiliary verb **'botega'** and it is stemmed from **'botag=to do'** which is derived from **'bo=do'**. The verb phrase, **'botegaa=have'** in the said sentence is a combination of two morphemes **'boteg'** and the inflection **'aa'**.

The argument **'hama=we'** takes up the place of the subject which sets off the work of gathering in the above-mentioned sentence. We claim here that the submission of information is dealt by the agent of the verb in the sentence. Information is sent by an agent to a certain form that is accountable for causing an incident to happen. As a result, it is known that this argument is the agent or actor because of doing an action. In this example, the sentence carries a single argument (we) assigning an agent theta role in consort with an agentive thematic relation by the predicate (verb). The adverbial phrase **'marchi=today'** shows the time of action.

Table 3: Example (5) presents a transitive verb in Balochi sentence, the arguments (NPs) of the predicates (VPs).

Sentence	Sentence
Description	
Roman script	<i>Mn wanag yal kota</i>
Transliteration	<i>mn=I; wanag=studies; yal kota=have left</i>
Translation	<i>I have left the studies.</i>

The verb phrase **'yal kota=have left'** is a preverbal verb in Balochi, the verb which is adding an extra component or comes before the verb to change the fundamental meaning of the verb. The aforementioned verb is a transitive verb, and it has two arguments to discuss about. The verb phrase **'yal kota=have left'** is a combination of an adjective **'yal=free'** and a simple verb **'kota'** which is the second form of the verb **'kanag=to do'** have different meanings individually but when they come together as **'yal kota'** (left) becomes a preverbal verb as leave. The verb **'yal kota'** is derived from the infinitive **'yal kanag'** which means (to leave). The verb phrase of the corresponding verb **'yal kota=have left'** is composition of two morphemes, a free morpheme **'yal kot=left'** accompanied by a bound morpheme **'a'** or shows (inflection), a copula suffix **'a'** is attached with the stem of the main verb **'yal kot+a'** which becomes **'yal kota'** from **'yal kanag'**, and finally the inflection shows that the tense is present perfect.

The argument **'mn=I'** is allocated an agent theta role while the argument **'wanag=studies'** gets the theme theta role by the verb. The agent is consistently assigned to the external argument position across all natural languages. This argument initiates an action. As a result, it is considered to be the agent of the verb. Therefore, it gets an agent theta role as well as an agentive thematic relation.

The other argument is **'wanag=studies'**. This is the argument that has undergone the action (have left). As the entire action is carried out in support of this argument, it serves as the sentence's main focus. It reveals that the subject has stopped studying. As a result, it takes a theme theta role as well as theme thematic relation by the verb phrase (VP).

Table 4: Example (6) presents ditransitive verb in Balochi sentence, the arguments (NPs) of the

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis of predicates (VPs).

Sentence	Sentence
Description	
Roman script	mara mat dem da kaleja
Transliteration	mara=we/us; mat=mother, send; da=does; kalej=college; a=to
Translation	Mother sends us to the college.

The verb phrase **'dem da=will send'** has three arguments **'mat=mother, 'mara=we/us'** and **'kalej=college'** one at subject position and the other two at object position in the sentence. The verb phrase **'dem da=sends'** is the first form which is a derivative form of the infinitive **'dem dayag=to send'**. The inflection (INFL) is attached with the main verb to show the aspect of the tense. Therefore, through this inflection **'da'**, it is to be noted that the tense is present simple.

The first argument **'mat=mother'** is a common noun. The action of sending **'them to a college'** is carried out by this argument. It has competence to accomplish something therefore this subject or argument is the agent of the verb. This argument is the semantic members of the predicate (verb) **'sent'** and its main syntactic arguments- the subject and the object. The verb gives this argument an agent theta role.

The action focuses on the argument **'mara=us'**. It takes up the place of the object. It must be noted that the argument **'mara=us'** is considered to be the theme because it goes through the process of being (sent). As a result, the verb allots a theme theta role as well as a theme thematic relation. The verb also allots this argument as the beneficiary because it receives benefits from the argument **'mat=mother'** (being sent to a college). As a result, this argument gets the beneficiary thematic relation by the verb in the said sentence.

The other argument **'کالج=kalej=college'** is basically a common noun and lacks the ability to perform an action. It just serves to finish the sentence as an object complement. As a result, it cannot be said that it is the theme. On the other hand, it is possible to claim that the action may start in one location and terminate in another location. Consequently, this argument is regarded as the sentence's goal and is given the goal theta role in consort with goal thematic relation. Finally, this argument is situated somewhere and for this reason the verb also donates locative theta role in consort with locative thematic relation.

Table 5: Example (7) presents transitive verb in Balochi sentence, the arguments (NPs) of the predicates (VPs).

Sentence	Sentence
Description	
Roman script	mani brass Future Stars Academy a wani
Transliteration	mani=my; brass=brother; Future Stars Academy; a=in wani=study
Translation	My brother will study in Future Stars Academy.

The verb phrase **'wani=will study'** has two arguments **'mani brass=my brother'** and **'Future Stars Academy'**. In nature the verb 'study' is both transitive as well as intransitive verb. The first form of the verb, **'wanan'** or **'wani'** has literary taken from the infinitive **'واننگ=wanag=to study'**. The inflection (INFL) is attached with the stem of the main verb **'(i)'** reveals that first

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

person singular is the subject whether male or female because there is no gender marker in Balochi language. However, this inflection also shows the aspect of the tense which is future simple tense.

The first argument '**mani brass=my brother**' is a common name. This argument carries out the activity of studying in a school. Hence, it is capable of studying in a school and therefore the verb allots this argument an agent theta role as well as an agent thematic relation.

The other argument '**Future Stars Academy**' is a name of school located in Tasp Panjgur. This argument does not carry out an action, it also does not proceed through an action. It just completes the sentence by acting as an object complement. As a result, it is not claimed to be called the sentence's theme. However, it is possible to claim that this noun phrase is also the goal of the verb for the reason that the action might take place or start from one location and terminate in another location.

Table 6: Example (8) presents transitive verb in Balochi sentence, the arguments (NPs) of the predicates (VPs).

Sentence Description	Sentence	
Roman script	mn <u>káh</u> cha bazara zore	
Transliteration	mn=I; <u>káh</u> =grass; cha=from; bazara=bazar, zore=buy.	The verb phrase ' zore=buy ' allots three theta roles or may be more than three
VP Analysis	Kind=transitive, tense=present, aspect=present simple, mood=simple	
Translation	I buy grass from bazar.	

thematic relations to the noun phrases. The arguments are '**mn=I**' as well as '**káh=grass**' in consort with a prepositional phrase '**cha bazara=from bazar**'. This context illustrates that the association suggested by thematic roles are frequently captured by prepositions. The verb phrase '**zore=buy**' is derivative form of the infinitive '**zorag/zirag**' which means 'to buy'. This is the first form of the verb that is used for present/future tense. The bound morpheme '**e**' is attached with the stem of the main verb '**zor=buy**'. The inflection shows the tense, aspect, or number.

The first argument '**mn=I**' occupies the place of a subject which is a nominative pronoun. This argument states the role of an agent or an actor. This argument makes a task of (buying grass). This argument causes or prompts the action in a sentence. Therefore, the verb assigns this argument an agent theta role. Thus, it also gets an agentive thematic relation.

The verb also illustrates that the second argument is '**káh=grass**'. It is in fact a direct object. This is the object that the subject acts upon in the sentence. This argument as being inanimate which cannot do any sort of action. However, it undergoes an action (buy). As a result, the verb phrase gives theme theta role along with theme thematic relation to this argument.

The prepositional phrase '**cha bazara=from bazar**' fills the thematic role of location; it is the location from which grass is bought. The structure of the sentence also states that there is neither an action done by this argument, nor an action is undergone by this argument. Therefore, this argument has locative theta role as well as locative thematic relation.

Table 7: Example (10) presents transitive verb in Balochi sentence, the arguments (NPs) of the

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis of predicates (VPs).

Sentence Description	Sentence
Roman script	Mn tae golgedara geren.
Transliteration	mn=I; tae=you; golgedar=interview; geren=take; a=agreement.
Translation	I will take your interview.

The verb phrase '**geren=will take**' is a transitive verb in nature. Verb '**geren=will take**' is the first form which is derivative form of the infinitive '**gerag=to**'. The inflection is attached with the main verb to show the aspect of the tense. Therefore, through this inflection '**en**', it is to be noted that the aspect of the tense is present/future.

The argument '**mn=I**' is the one who does the action of conducting an interview either in present or in the future. It takes up the place of subject. It plays as the role of an actor and therefore this argument gets an agent theta role by the verb in consort with an agentive thematic relation.

On the other hand, the argument '**tae golgedara=your interview**' is referred as the theme which is being focused in the sentence and thereby gets a theme theta role as well as a theme thematic relation by the verb. This argument is also the goal of the verb for the reason that it is the entity regarding of the action that takes place. Therefore, the verb also donates the goal thematic relation to this argument.

Table 8: Example (11) presents transitive verb in Balochi sentence, the arguments (NPs) of the predicates (VPs).

Sentence Description	Sentence
Roman script	Marocha mn pootball gowazi kaney
Transliteration	marocha=nowadays; mn=I; pootball=football; gowazi=play; kane=do.
Translation	Nowadays I play football.

The verb phrase '**gowazi kane=play**' is a transitive verb. The term '**gowazi=play/game** in Balochi is a noun, or alone used as a noun but when it comes with '**kane**' together it then acts as a verb phrase. Therefore, this verb acts as preverbal in Balochi, the verbs which are having of a verb together with a pre-verb which is adding an extra component of location or direction to the fundamental semantic of the verb. This verb phrase is derivative form of the infinitive '**gowazi kanag= to play**'. Moreover, this inflection (INFL) states the subject and tense.

The above-mentioned verb has two arguments denoted by the verb. The arguments are '**mn=I**' and '**pootball=football**' gets agent as well as theme theta roles by the verb. The adverbial phrase '**marocha=nowadays**' shows the time of action.

The first argument is '**mn=I**'. Consequently, it can be claimed that this argument is the agent of the verb because it initiates an action. Therefore, the verb gives this argument an agent theta role in consort with an agentive thematic relation in the above-mentioned sentence.

This sentence also illustrates that the object of the sentence is '**pootball=football**' which is identified as the theme. However, the sentence's context further explains that the narrow

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

focus is the argument '**pooball=football**' because whole conversation is concentrated on this argument of the above given sentence. Finally, we refer this argument as being assigned a theme theta role as well as a theme thematic relation by the verb.

Table 9: Example (12) presents transitive verb in Balochi sentence.

Sentence	Sentence
Description	
Roman script	Zee hama Paan-z-dhah kapoot shikar korte ga
Transliteration	Zee=yesterday; hama=we; Paan-z-dhah =fifteen; kapoot=dove; shikar=hunt; korte, ga=agreement
Translation	Yesterday, we had hunted 15 doves.

The verb phrase '**shikar korte ga= had hunted**' is a transitive verb. This verb phrase is a derivative form of the infinitive '**shikar kanag=to hunt**'. The main verb of this sentence is '**shikar=hunt**' and it has a double constructed verb or auxiliary verb that is used to show the aspect or tense. There are two bound morphemes, (**korte**) and (**ga**). Both of these inflections represent the aspects or the tense. However, the attached bound morpheme (**korte**) represents that the tense is past, and the other attached bound morpheme (**ga**) represents that the aspect is perfect.

The above-mentioned verb has two arguments denoted by the verb '**shikar korte ga= had hunted**'. The arguments '**hama=we**' and '**Paan-z-dhah kapoot= fifteen doves**' are allotted an agent as well as a theme theta role by the predicate.

The second person plural pronoun '**hama=we**' is considered to be the first argument of the said sentence that carried out an action of (hunting) of birds (doves). This argument is engaged in an action of (hunting). Therefore, the verb ascertains an agent theta role in consort with an agentive thematic relation to this argument in the above given sentence.

The other argument '**Paan-z-dhah kapoot= fifteen doves**' is the object or the theme of the sentence because the argument had undergone an action of (hunting). Therefore, the theme is being concentrated in the sentence as it is used as an object in the given sentence. Hence, we can refer this argument as a theme assigning a theme theta role as well as theme thematic relation.

Table 10: Example (13) presents transitive verb in Balochi sentence.

Sentence	Sentence
Description	
Roman script	hao mana teacher a shar wanenta
Transliteration	hao=yes ; mana=me; teachera=teachers, shar=well; wanent=taught; a=had
Translation	Yes, teachers had taught me well.

The verb phrase '**wanenta=had taught**' is used as transitive verb with two arguments to be discussed. It is a combination of two morphemes '**wanent=taught**', which is a free morpheme and the other one is a bound morpheme '**a=had**' that comes with the stem of the main verb so as to show the aspect of the tense. The base form of verb '**wanenta=had taught**' is '**wanenag=to teach**'. The third form of the verb is used in this sentence because the aspect is perfect of the past tense. The arguments are: '**teachera=teachers**', and '**mana=me**' holding two theta roles source, theme, and beneficiary.

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

The first argument '*teachera=teachers*' specifies the sentence's source, and it is a single pronoun occupies the place of subject (a person). This argument has the source theta role so as to demonstrate that it shows that something is happening in the said sentence. As a result, the source thematic relation for this argument is allotted by the verb in the said sentence. Moreover, this argument is the reason or initiator to an event (the act of teaching). Therefore, it gets an agent thematic relation too.

The second argument is '*mana=me*'. This is the argument that has undergone the action (was taught well) by the teachers. It is the nominative case of '*T*'. It expresses that the subject was taught by teachers. Thus, the argument '*←mana=me*' is considered to be the theme of the said sentence. As a result, it gets a theme theta role as well as the theme and beneficiary thematic relations.

Findings and Discussion

The immense purpose of this study is to establish the argument structure of the Balochi language. Based on this, the researchers strive to determine, investigate, and explore the analytical and descriptive study of argument structure, the assignment of agent and theme theta roles and thematic relations which are assigned to various arguments of the predicates. The results of the prospective research contribute to supporting the previous study on argument structure in terms of theta roles. During the study, the investigators have set up and revealed the native speakers of Rakshani dialects, utilizing, uttering argument structure, and connecting it with the assignment of agent as well as theme theta roles in consort with their thematic relations in their daily discussions as well as conversations. The analysis of the current study also validated the kinds of verbs in Balochi language.

The analysis of the data proves that the arguments in Balochi sentences are assigned to agent as well as theme theta roles denoted by the predicates in the sentences. After the analysis, descriptive and exploration of the questions, it has been proved that Balochi language is rich in assigning theta roles to various arguments of the verbs in the sentences. Theta Criterion Theory states that each argument receives a single theta role and vice versa (Haegeman, 1994; & Carnie, 2007).

The researcher has also strained to highlight the roles of the free morphemes, bound morphemes/inflections/derivations which are attached with the stem/root of the main verbs which resultantly helps to regain, infer, and identify the number, person, tense, and aspect of Balochi verbs.

Conclusion

This study purely focuses on Makrani dialects of Balochi language in respect to argument structure, the assignment of agent and theme theta roles as well as thematic Relations. This study has successfully used the above theory of Carnie (2007) on the verbs of Balochi language in terms of argument structure and thematic structure. Every language has different structure of sentences, and the number of theta roles varies from language to language.

The analysis also finds that Balochi language is enrich in having all of the 9 theta roles that are projected by Carnie in 2007. However, this research only deals in the analysis of the assignment of agent and theme theta roles to the arguments of the Balochi verbs. Balochi is also like English; the arguments are assigned the thematic roles ascertained by the types of

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

the verbs. The results of the current study align with Shazia, Z. A., & Gulkhanda, 2022; Pathan, M. S. K. (2023), Veesar, et al., 2015b; Pathan, M. S. K. (2022); Veesar, et al., 2015a; Veesar & Mustafa, 2021; Pathan, M. S. K. (2022) .

Contribution of the study

The analytical study of argument structure in Balochi language has proved that Balochi language may be further remarkably investigated and researched in the field of Syntax, Semantics as well as Pragmatics. These fields keep this language under consideration for research study which can be enormously prosperous for the progress, development, and construction of the Balochi language. This study may be helpful for the society and for Balochi language as well. In the meantime, this analytical study will capture praiseworthy opportunities to bring to the world of linguists a very prominent and key feature for this vital language. It will not give advantages to Balochi language only; it will also be a standard work for many other languages. Simultaneously, it will also be an appreciated study for those students who desired to do their research in the area of syntax.

References

1. Ackerman, F., & Malouf, Robert. (2013). Morphological Organization: The Low Conditional Entropy Conjecture. *Journal of Language*, 89(3), 429-464. doi: 10.1353/lan.2013.0054
2. Ahmed, M., & Veesar, Z. A. (2022). Exploration of Balochi as a Pro-Drop Language. *Erevna: Journal of Linguistics and Literature*, 6(1), 113-126.
3. Ali, Z. (2021). Article A Comparative Study of Locative, Source, Goal and Instrumentive Thematic Relations in English and Sindhi. *University of Chitral Journal of Linguistics & Literature*, 5(II), 237-255.
4. Ali, Z., & Azam, M. (2021). A Morphological Analysis of Transitive and Intransitive Verbs in Lasi. *Harf-o-Sukhan*, 5(3), 346-356.
5. Ali, Z., Roonjho, Z., & Brohi, F. M. (2021). A Comparison of the Lasi language with English. *Progressive Research Journal of Arts & Humanities (PRJAH)*, 3(2).
6. Axenov, S. (2003). *The Balochi Language in Turkmenistan*. The Baloch and their Neighbours, 245-258.
7. Badal Khan, S., & Jahani, C. (2013). *A Brief Introduction to Balochi Literature*.
8. Bagudu, R. S., Ali, Z., & Kadhim, K. A. (2015) Description and Analysis of Javanese Language Noun Phrases in [wh] Questions. *Balochistan Journal of Linguistics ISSN 2312-5454 (2015 Issue 3)*, 29.
9. Baker, M. C. (1997). Thematic Roles and Syntactic Structure *In Elements of Grammar* (pp. 73-137). Netherlands: Springer Netherlands.
10. Bashir, E. L. (1991). *A Contrastive Analysis of Balochi and Urdu*: Academy for Educational Development.
11. Borik, O., & Mateu, Jaume. (2014). Argument structure in morphology and syntax: An introduction. *Lingua* (141), 1-7. doi: 10.1016/j.lingua.2014.01.004
12. Carnie, A. (2007). *Syntax: A Generative Introduction* (B. P. Ltd Ed. Second ed. Vol. 1). London: Blackwell Publishing, UK, USA, Australia.
13. Carnie, A. (2011a). Mixed categories in Irish. *Lingua*, 121(7), 1207-1224. doi: 10.1016/j.lingua.2011.01.013
14. Carnie, A. (2011b). The locative syntax of experiencers. *Language*, 87(2), 409-411
15. Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (V. Knight Ed.). USA: Sage publications.
16. Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*.

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

(4th edition (March 14, 2013) ed. Vol. 1). USA: SAGE

17. Dowty, D. (1991). Thematic Proto-Roles and Argument Selection. *Language*, 67(3), 547-619. doi: 10.2307/415037
18. Elfenbein, J. (1989). *Balochistan III: Balochi Language and Literature*. Encyclopaedia Iranica III, 633-644.
19. Grimshaw, J. (1990). *Argument Structure*. US: Cambridge, Massachusetts: MIT Press.
20. Haegeman, L. (1994). *Introduction to Government & Binding Theory* (B. P. Ltd Ed. Second Edition ed.). UK & USA: Blackwell Oxford UK & Cambridge USA.
21. Haegeman, L. (2013). The syntax of registers: Diary subject omission and the privilege of the root. *Journal of Lingua*, 130, 88-113.
22. Hammer, A., Coene, M., Rooryck, J., & Govaerts, P. J. (2014). The production of Dutch finite verb morphology: A comparison between hearing-impaired CI children and specific language impaired children. *Lingua*, 139, 68-79. doi: 10.1016/j.lingua.2013.11.010
23. Hovav, M. R., Levin, B., Beavers, J., Sichel, I., & Tham, S. W. (2007). Deconstructing thematic hierarchies. Architectures, rules, and preferences: Variations on themes by Joan W. Bresnan, CSLI Publications, Stanford, CA, 385-402.
24. Jackendoff, R. (1987). The Status of Thematic Relations in Linguistic Theory. *Linguistic inquiry*, 18(3), 369-411.
25. Jahani, C. (2003). *The case system in Iranian Balochi in a contact linguistic perspective*.
26. Khan, S., Ali, Z., & Jan, D. (2022). Morphological Properties of Balochi Verbs. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 4(2), 155-167.
27. Khoso, A. A., & Pathan, M. S. K. (2023). The Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in The Relationship Between Organizational Culture and Employee Commitment in Islamic Banking. *International Research Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 4(3), 24-41.
28. Kumar, R. (2011). *Research Methodology: A step by step Guide for Beginners*. Loss Angles, USA: SAGE.
29. Levin, B., & Hovav, M. R. (2005). *Argument realization* (First ed.). UK & USA: Cambridge University Press.
30. Mackenzie (1961) *The Origins of Kurdish," Kurdish Dialect Studies*, 2 vols. (London Oriental Series, 9 and 10, Oxford University Press), 1961-62.
31. Muhammad, S. K. P. (2023). THE INFLUENCE OF ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE ON EMPLOYEE COMMITMENT AND TURNOVER INTENTIONS: A STUDY OF THE IMPORTANCE OF POSITIVE CULTURE FOR RETAINING EMPLOYEES. *Global Research Journal of Management and Social Sciences (GRJMSS)*, 1(1), 85-94.
32. Neuman, W. L. (2005). *Social research methods: Quantitative and qualitative approaches* (Vol. 13): Allyn and Bacon Boston.
33. Pathan, M. S. K. (2022). The Role of Social Capital in Promoting Entrepreneurial Success. *International Research Journal of Education and Innovation*, 3(3), 8-16.
34. Pathan, M. S. K. (2023). Assessing the mediating role of job satisfaction in the relationship between organizational culture and employee commitment. *International Research Journal of Education and Innovation*, 4(1), 1-11.
35. Pathan, M. S. K., & Khoso, A. A. (2023). Misfortune Tragedy Findings in Pakistan: A Public Learning Perspective on Virtue of Economic Recovery Mindset. *International Research Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 4(3), 12-23.
36. Publications, Inc.
37. Rasheed, A., Ali, Z., & Khan, K. A. (2023). A Morphosyntactic Analysis of Suffixation in Lasi and Sindhi. *Pakistan Journal of Society, Education and Language (PJSEL)*, 9(2), 334-346.
38. Shad, G. (2011). *Shahdain Balochi*. Panjgur. Azzat Academy Panjgur.
39. Shazia, Z. A., & Gulkhanda, S. (2022). A Morphosyntactic Analysis of Kalati Brahui

Agent and Theme Theta Roles in Balochi: A Morphosemantic Analysis

Verbs. *Competitive Social Science Research Journal*, 3(2), 74-87.

40. Veesar, Z. A., & Mustafa, G. (2021). A Comparative Analysis of Retroflexion in Romani and Lasi: NA. *JEHR Journal of Education and Humanities Research, University of Balochistan*, 11(1), 78-95.
41. Veesar, Z. A., Kadhim, K. A., & Bagudu, R. S. (2015). The Most Prominent Theta Roles in the Sindhi Language: The Hierarchy. *International Journal of Foreign Language Teaching and Research*, 3(12), 11-24.
42. Veesar, Z. A., Srinivass, S., & Kadhim, K. A. (2015). A Comparison of Theme Theta Roles in English and Sindhi. *Language & Communication*, 2(1), 77-89.
43. Zahid, A. (2016). Morphosemantic and syntactic analysis of verbs in Sindhi/Zahid Ali (Doctoral dissertation, University of Malaya).